

Play, Four Days and a 1/4 ton of Clay

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Abstract

This paper explores the use of play as a catalyst for creativity. Freud suggests that “The creative writer [designer] does the same as the child at play. He creates a world of fantasy which he takes very seriously - that is, which he invests with large amounts of emotion.”

Play is an unavoidable and essential element in the design process, but one which is largely ignored. The dry, reductionist view of design that seeks to promote the designer as an objective, emotionless entity struggles when looking for explanations of recent design trends. It is argued that play is an essential part of the creative process, and one that is ignored at great cost. This is illustrated through several recent industrial/product design examples as well as a recent example of a group, mass-participation creative endeavour (film to be shown of ‘Claystation’ event held at Designersblock 2003 – long standing London-based showcase of innovative, independent design). This begins to explore the role of an audience in the appreciation of design, to suggest that authorship is not always everything, and that creativity can be explored through the ephemeral.

Keywords: play element in design, participation, creativity, user-complicity.

The designer’s job is often described in terms of a linear process through which projects develop. The professionalisation of this has invited comparisons with other industries that define their operation along fairly strict and inflexible lines. As soon as one starts to espouse creativity as a core element in this process, however, as is the case with design, it becomes more difficult to reproduce reliably: thankfully no one can yet agree on a foolproof approach to creative thought.[1] Creativity is an accepted element of the process of design, but the understanding of what informs this falls a long way short. Definitions range from the prosaic to the mystical but there is little consensus, and it has persistently eluded precise categorization. One of the most helpful definitions is ‘thinking differently;’ many so-called creativity techniques are simply tools for encouraging one to do this (Buzan 1974, De Bono 1990); to adopt a different perspective on a particular problem or issue and develop lines of thought or argument in relation to this. This is remarkably similar to descriptions that have been given over the years of play. In fact pretty much everything that has been written about creativity stresses the same points – that it requires a suspension of existing patterns of engagement and the adoption of uncharacteristic roles within scenarios that are governed by strict rules. In other words, play. The psychologist Carl Jung tells us: “The creation of

something new is not accomplished by the intellect but by the play instinct acting from inner necessity. The creative mind plays with the objects it loves (Ackerman 2000: 121).” This argument seems fairly natural and familiar to designers, although the play element of their work may be ‘underplayed’ in the professional context.

This paper attempts to develop this link between play and design, and to ask why they are not more familiar bedfellows. It looks at contemporary examples of a playful approach in design and the arts. It considers the portrayal of design in the media and asks whether a purely reverential approach is entirely appropriate. Finally it introduces a project that attempts to engage audiences for design in creative, playful, activity.

It has been observed that moments of creative enlightenment often occur when they are least expected. Strategies for generating ideas are usually associated with freeing the mind from the immediate concerns of a project or problem and immersing oneself in a completely different activity. This may be walking the dog or cleaning the house, or perhaps something more energetic such as cycling or rock climbing. Newton famously, perhaps apocryphally, conceived his understanding of gravity from a falling apple. Agatha Christie developed her plot lines whilst washing up. It’s not the washing up or the apple that’s important here; it could have been anything. What matters is that these are examples of a development process that has been accelerated through contemplation outside typical, or routine lines of thought. That is not to say that anyone engaging in these activities alone will deliver novel theories or even novels. It is simply an acknowledgement that the brain is often at its most productive when engaged in processing that doesn’t conform to a linear mode of progression. This processing might well be described as ‘daydreaming’ in these cases, but there is also evidence that it arises out of activities categorized as ‘play.’ Either way, they are far removed from what one might think of as ‘useful,’ or aligned to a protestant work ethic, where hard work equals reward. This has been reinforced in education, literature and philosophy for centuries, to the extent that it has become well-established as an ideology and form of control. There is something subversive and threatening to agencies of power in the notion of adults ‘playing:’ it has even been linked to the counter-culture movement, and political activism in the 1960’s (Neville 1970).

This has probably not always been the case: there is some evidence that adults in ancient societies played many of the same games as children, or that a playful attitude, at least, was

desirable and profitable in the creation of culture (Cohen 1993:18). Serious research into play, however, since the 1950's has concentrated on three main areas: firstly, the analysis of play as a means of developing manual and cognitive skills, secondly, in the development of social skills, and thirdly, as a therapeutic aid to tackle developmental problems (Klein 1959, Winnicott, 1974). This 'serious' approach becomes somewhat counter-productive when it comes to sanctioning playful activity for its own sake. The clinical study of the subject reinforces a view that it is something that 'normal' children engage in before growing up, and that it is a regrettable, but necessary by-product of physical and social development. This is a step forward from Victorian moral standards, which did all it could to sweep the whole notion of 'childhood' under the carpet. But it is a long way from a celebration, or encouragement, of play; especially for adults.

This position was famously challenged by Johan Huizinga in his 1946 work, 'Homo Ludens.' In this, Huizinga proposed the theory that play was integral to the creation of culture; that all significant cultural phenomena are based upon it. He cites a multitude of historic precedent to deliver his argument, at the same time challenging the dominant attitude present in psychology that play is simply a tool through which individuals (children) learn and test certain life skills. Huizinga suggests that the spirit of play is evident in all cultural, artistic and philosophical pursuits and that these form the basis of civilisation. He defines this as: "...a free activity standing quite consciously outside 'ordinary' life as being 'not serious,' but at the same time absorbing the player intensely and utterly. It is an activity connected with no material interest and no profit can be gained by it. It proceeds within its own boundaries of time and space according to fixed rules and in an orderly manner. It promotes the formation of social groupings which tend to surround themselves with secrecy and to stress their difference from the common world by disguise or other means (Huizinga 1949:13)." There seems to have been a re-discovery of this point-of-view in recent times, with play being celebrated in places normally reserved for more detached contemplation. Two recent examples in London being the Commonwealth exhibition at the Tate Modern and the State of Play exhibition at the Serpentine Gallery [3]. Both purport the celebration of play as a creative tool, with works in the Commonwealth exhibition actively encouraging audience participation. Works by Gabriel Orozco among others lent the gallery the air of a youth club designed by Salvador Dali. So unusual and popular were these works that they were nearly always out of order.

Unfortunately getting people involved in play activity is not always so simple. By its very nature it is something that is entered into voluntarily; whilst it may not have any useful outcomes, it must be seen to have some marginal benefit, i.e. it must be fun. This is where most play strategies fall down: creating the conditions for play is more than just providing the toys. It is about understanding the motivations behind it, and the latent benefits to participants. A useful development of these ideas, therefore, might be “Flow” (Csikszentmihalyi 1994). In all play there is an element of flow, but because it describes a state of mind rather than a particular pursuit, we can consider various means of achieving it. One might feel uncomfortable describing the activity of brain surgeons, politicians or athletes as play (as Huizinga might), but it is easier to conclude that they experience “flow.” This is the state in which all mental and physical faculties are working in harmony with their surroundings, where the demands on each are significant even challenging, but where they may be overcome through the confidence of years of training and experience. Csikszentmihalyi’s ‘discovery’ is that happiness does not depend on external influence, but rather on an individual’s perception, or interpretation, of these - in particular a level of involvement with a task or activity. This originates with the Aristotelean assumption that above anything else, humanity strives to achieve ‘happiness.’ This may be an important connection to make, as it has the potential to inform the way particular tasks or activities are constructed, whether for educational or enjoyment purposes. He cites examples of a sailor on a tight course or someone living through a particularly traumatic experience, observing that it is in these situations that people often receive extraordinarily rich transformative epiphanies (Csikszentmihalyi 1994: 3). The fact that these are not passive, receptive or relaxing times meshes with the observation that play for children is not always a pleasurable experience. It also starts to explain the growth of industries that offer experiences as opposed to more straightforward services.

In ‘The Experience Economy’ authors Joseph Pine and James Gilmore propose that as cultures become more sophisticated, so they come to seek ‘higher’ forms of stimulus. This is evidenced through the shift in employment from business that produce goods to those that provide service, and subsequently to those that create experiences. These companies can be said to be offering a degree of ‘flow;’ that going on safari, white-water rafting, or learning to paint all require a level of investment from the participant in the form of discomfort, fear, patience etc. in order to gain any benefit. At the other extreme we might consider watching television, which rarely demands any form of engagement, and is almost wholly passive. At

this level, any notion of 'flow' gives way to a state of Psychic Entropy. This, Csikszentmihalyi says, is what forms the barrier to consciousness, or the ability "...to represent information about what is happening outside and inside the organism in such a way that it can be evaluated and acted upon by the body. In this sense it functions as a clearinghouse for sensations, perceptions, feelings, and ideas, establishing priorities among all the diverse information (Csikszentmihalyi 1994: 24)." It is precisely this aspect of consciousness that is so sought after by designers. It is the ability to look at problems, issues and situations from a variety of positions, to make sense of these, and to create meaningful connections around them. When the Design Transformation Group (DTG) was set up, it had the aim of re-introducing these notions, and 'ways of seeing' to the core of design practice. There is no doubt that flow is experienced by designers at certain times, but very often the pressures of demand and deadlines get in the way and stifle the production of innovative, or truly creative work. These ways of seeing extend to the contemplation, engagement and critique of contemporary design work.

It has been suggested above that a creative approach to problems and issues stems from an underlying desire to be playful. This has extended in recent years beyond the immediate process of design into the hands of the audience or consumers of this design. Objects created by docreate [4], for instance, invite the user to take an active part in the process of creation, by providing 'half-finished,' or 'incomplete' solutions into which a further injection of creative intervention is required. Examples include the 'do hit' chair, fig 1., by Marijn van der Poll, which is supplied as a cube of sheet metal which needs to be beaten into shape by the consumer, or 'do cut,' by Radi Designers/Robert Stadler, supplied as a contoured tubular moulding which can be chopped up into sections to make vases, umbrella stands, hair grips, salad bowls.... This example is from a fairly experimental stance, whose audience is undeniably 'design-savvy.' When one starts to look for it, however, the same strategy can be observed in the most unlikely places. Even Ikea have been at it [5]. This engagement with what has been termed 'Marcel Duchamp meets Martha Stewart' (Hunt 2003: 66), is clearly in line with what Pine and Gilmore predicted in 'The Experience Economy' – that 'transformative,' or productive experiences would come to replace those that are more passive. Clearly design and creativity fall into these categories and can be seen to be increasingly desirable or aspirational.

Figure 1, “do hit” by Marijn van der Poll. Photograph by Bianca Pilet

One of the problems of the designer is how to effectively engage their audience, who are more likely to want these objects kept in their ‘raw’ state, and who are more comfortable with consuming design in the same way as art – at a comfortable distance. This is one of the issues that has been tackled recently by the London-based organisation Designersblock. Since 1994 their events have been a showcase and proving ground for up and coming design talent in a variety of disciplines. It has emerged as the most influential and exciting forum for the promotion of innovative work that it has earned a worldwide reputation. Exhibitions have so far been held in Milan, Barcelona and Tokyo, as well as London, with founders Piers Roberts and Rory Dodd being brave enough to experiment with the format and presentation of design, so that the events are in the process of constant reinvention, whilst maintaining a core philosophy of pioneering the interests of the designers it exhibits.

It is difficult to pinpoint the moment at which industrial design, as opposed to decorative arts, came to be consumed in ways outside a purely commercial context. The founding of the Boilerhouse at the Victoria and Albert Museum in 1982 was probably a key moment, as was the subsequent transplant of this into the Design Museum, which opened its doors in 1989. But the Museum of Modern Art, New York began collecting furniture in 1933. These

institutions have pretty much always adopted means of curation which invite the visitor to revere, rather than revel. A venue for the celebration of design has proven very similar to that of art, i.e. "...constructed along laws as rigorous as those for building a medieval church. The outside world must not come in, so windows are usually sealed off. Walls are painted white. The ceiling becomes the source of light. The wooden floor is polished so that you click along clinically, or carpeted so that you pad soundlessly, resting the feet while the eyes have at the wall. The art is free, as the saying used to go 'to take on its own life.'" (O'Docherty 1986: 15)

As a concession, the Design Museum allows some of its chairs to be sat in, and it positively encourages one to buy the work it has sanctioned in its shop. Beyond this, however, is a fairly uniform landscape of vitrines and plinths that place a clear barrier between the consumer and the consumed. While the function of art in this context has always been a subject for debate, with design it becomes doubly so. The 'minefield of vested interests' that arises out of a situation where the objects being revered are also available to buy, is a difficult one for the curator to navigate (Usherwood 1995: 267). In some ways the art world has more of a track record for innovation in this area. A notable figure was Friedrich Kiesler, who designed many exhibitions including the "Art of This Century" for Peggy Guggenheim in 1942. This included many *interactive* exhibits showcasing the work of contemporary surrealist artists. He created one gallery called the "Kinetic Gallery" and installed "Vision Machines" for the works of Paul Klee and Marcel Duchamp. Some of the galleries even included Kiesler's own "Correalist Furniture," which were designed to combat the problem of fatigue during a visit to the gallery (Cantz 2003). Despite precedent such as this, though, design is nearly always offered for consumption in a dry, clinical manner that does not invite interaction on any level.

As a result, Designersblock have taken the initiative to start to innovate in this area. They have deliberately introduced elements into their shows that are intended to draw their audience in and encourage participation and debate. Along with the promotion of designers in their exhibitions, Designersblock have an agenda to try and engage people with design thinking at a deep level. Co-founder Piers Roberts explains the choice of title for their events: "The name reflects where we are at in the sense of overcoming blocks and obstacles that stand in the way of progress in design and design thinking... I am interested in the interaction with place in particular, and offering spaces outside the conventional where people can engage with design at a new level [6]." During the 2003 Milan Designersblock, there was a park bench exhibited alongside a variety of engraving and carving tools. Visitors were

encouraged to gouge names and messages in the chair during the course of the event. During the 2003 London exhibition[7] a giant paint-by-numbers picture was hung in the entrance, which was gradually filled in by visitors. At the same event there was another exhibit, “Claystation,” (Figures 1 and 2) at which visitors’ creative energies were focused towards the creation of a claymation film.

Figure 2, “Claystation” at Designersblock London, 2003

Over the duration of the exhibition (the ‘four days’ of the title), visitors were encouraged to purchase a lump of Plasticine (the ‘1/4 ton of clay’ in the title) [8], and to spend as long as they wanted carving, sculpting, and forming it into whatever they desired. The resulting objects were placed on a ‘stage’ where their creators could manipulate them and interact with others’ creations. A camera mounted in the ceiling of the venue recorded these objects’ positions every 30 seconds. These were then compiled into a film of the whole event. With a complete absence of narrative, or constraint in expression, participants were completely free to experiment with the format. Piers Roberts observed: “Claystation fits our model of interaction as it is an invitation for people to cross a bridge where they can involve themselves with design ideas and processes. Play is an important element in these processes and one that is a strong motivating force when attempting to get people involved.”[7]. It became quickly apparent that this activity created a strong sense of ‘flow’ in those taking

part. This becomes clearer if we consider Csikszentmihalyi's definitions, of the eight principle components of enjoyment (Csikszentmihalyi 1992: 49):

1. The experience usually occurs when we confront tasks that we have a chance of completing.
2. We must be able to concentrate on what we are doing.
3. and 4. The concentration is usually possible because the task undertaken has clear goals and provides immediate feedback.
5. One acts with a deep but effortless involvement that removes from awareness the worries and frustrations of everyday life.
6. Enjoyable experiences allow people to exercise a sense of control over their actions.
7. Concern for the self disappears, yet paradoxically the sense of self emerges stronger after the flow experience is over.
8. The sense of the duration of time is altered; hours pass by in minutes and minutes can stretch out to seem like hours.

Figure 2, “Claystation” at Designersblock London, 2003

Over 300 visitors participated in this event over the course of the exhibition, creating a spectacle that was made into a film lasting more than 8 minutes. No attempt was made to

record individual visitor's contributions, but most stayed for between 20 and 40 minutes, with many returning after having visited the other parts of the exhibition. The film was deliberately left in an un-edited state, and, with the exception of the addition of a soundtrack, was left to unfold as it happened. As a result there are short bursts of plot line, but these quickly degenerate and decay as fresh participants take over. The subject, techniques and narrative of the animation could be studied endlessly, but the key lesson is one of how active engagement in an environment previously reserved for contemplation may be facilitated and encouraged. There is no doubt that both play and flow, as described, were taking place, and that a more beneficial appreciation of the experience was achieved [9]. This format has shown to be versatile and engaging within the context of a design exhibition, and is in the process of further refinement to be included at future events.

Credits:

Fig 1 reproduced by kind permission of do, an initiative of Kesselskramer.
photography, Bianca Pilet

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NOTES

[1] Perhaps the closest anyone has got is a system called Triz, developed by Genrich Altshuller in the 1940s. Based on a rigorous analysis of innovation through patent specification, it can reliably predict fruitful avenues of problem-solving. It does not 'solve' problems automatically, however, and relies on other creativity methods to make the transition from *generic* solutions to *specific* solutions. For more information see <http://www.triz.info/>

[2] Many different sources such as De Bono, E. (1990) *Six Thinking Hats*. London: Penguin, and Buzan, T. (1974) *Use Your Head*. London: BBC advocate an approach through which the individual approaches problems from novel positions.

Ackerman, Diane. 2000. *Deep Play*. New York: Random House International.

[3] Commonwealth at the Tate Modern, Bankside, London. 22nd October – 28th December, 2003. Including works by Jennifer Allora, Guillermo Caladilla, Thomas Hirschhorn, Carsten Holler and Gabriel Orozco. State of Play at the Serpentine Gallery, London. 3rd February – 28th March, 2004. Including works by Maurizio Cattelan, David Shrigley and Sarah Sze.

[4] 'do' is an experimental arm of Dutch advertising agency KesselsKramer ('do is an ever-changing brand that depends on what you do.' From their website <http://www.dcreate.com/>) do has been involved in several projects that seek to re-interpret the roles of the creative industries. One of these, dcreate involved Droog design in creating objects that sought new levels of user engagement.

[5] Beyond their well-established strategy of home-build and paint, the 2003 Ikea catalogue included a pendant lighting fixture called 'Ikea/PS' by H. Kjellberg and M. Lindqvist, – a bucket shaped shade in clear acrylic that invites the user to place objects around the light source not only to change its intensity and hue, but also as an expression of 'self.'

[6] Piers Roberts, interviewed by the author, March, 2004.

[7] Designersblock London, 2003, took place at the Tea Building, Bethnal Green Road, London, between 24th September and 28th September, 2003.

[8] Plasticine has a significant place in the history of Industrial Design, as the favoured modelling tool of pioneers such as Raymond Loewy. See: Schonberger, A. (Ed.). 1991. *Raymond Loewy - Pioneer of American Industrial Design*. London: Prestel.

[9] More details to be found at: <<http://www.claystation.org>>

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